

Annotation Scheme and Guidelines for Psychosocial Risk and Protective Factors in CSAM Prevention Interventions

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1. Data

The data annotated with this scheme were drawn from therapist-led, chat-based interventions conducted by the Institute of Sexology and Sexual Medicine at Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin as part of the *Troubled Desire* chat study. The study involves individuals who self-report being at risk of child sexual abuse material (CSAM) use and who represent an undetected, help-seeking population. Sessions lasted 50 minutes each, and clients typically participated in a four-session intervention. As an initial step, the data were automatically de-identified. Annotators therefore identify any Protected Health Information (PHI, according to HIPAA) remaining after automatic de-identification alongside the task-specific labels defined below.

2. Motivation

This annotation scheme is intended for a preventive, therapeutic, and non-forensic setting. It focuses on client and therapist language that may be informative for near-term CSAM relapse risk, with particular attention to psychosocial risk and protective factors that indicate whether the client appears more or less vulnerable to relapse in the near future. For the purposes of this work, relapse is defined as a self-reported return to CSAM-related behaviour since the previous session. Mentions of urges, thoughts, fantasies, or perceived risk alone are not sufficient unless accompanied by reported relapse behaviour.

The aim is not to make deterministic predictions, but to capture linguistically observable cues that can support structured, context-sensitive short-term risk estimation. The scheme is further intended to support the manual creation of a gold-standard dataset for training and evaluating automatic classifiers, with the longer-term goal of enabling a larger-scale corpus. In addition, the annotation of remaining PHI contributes to preparing the material for safer future corpus use and downstream modelling. Prospectively, such data may support tools that flag risk and protective factors in client talk, assist therapists during sessions, and facilitate longitudinal tracking of client progress over the course of an intervention.

3. Annotation Targets

The annotation task comprises four targets. At the document level, assign a **Relapse** label indicating whether relapse since the previous session is reported.

At the span level, annotate **Relapse Behavior**, **Risk and Protective Factors** according to the annotation scheme below. Additionally, annotate any remaining **PHI**.

Relapse Behavior	Mentions and descriptions of relapse behavior since the previous session.
Risk Factor	RF ; language indicating a factor that may increase vulnerability to relapse.
Protective Factor	PF ; language indicating a factor that may support stability and reduce vulnerability to relapse.

PHI Protected Health Information. We annotate PHI according to the [GeMTeX](#) guidelines (Lohr et al., 2024), which are based on the 18 PHI categories defined under HIPAA, such as names, dates, contacts, IDs, locations, and ages, and extend them by an additional profession category.

Examples: *“Sorry, **Dr. Smith**. It’s just hard to talk about this.”*
 *“Everything started when I lived at **742 Maplewood Drive**.”*
 *“I used to go by ‘**ShadowWolf92**’ on those forums.”*

4. Annotation Rules

- Read the entire document first to gain a general overview of the context before assigning any labels.
- Assign the document-level Relapse label to indicate whether relapse (CSAM use) since the previous session is reported.
- Read the document again and, selecting spans and assigning the corresponding layer and label, annotate the following categories:
 - Use the **Relapse Behavior** layer to annotate spans in which therapist and client explicitly discuss relapse behavior since the last session.
 - Annotate any remaining **PHI** according to the GeMTeX guidelines.
 - Annotate **Risk and Protective Factors** according to the annotation scheme.
- Annotate all occurrences of relevant information if it occurs multiple times in the text.
- Annotate all relevant information expressed in both client and therapist text. This includes, for example, therapist summaries, affirmations of commitment, clarification questions, and literal reformulations of what the client wrote. If the therapist misunderstands something, the respective span should still be annotated.
- Prefer marking the smallest span necessary to capture the relevant meaning. Do not mark whole sentences unless the full sentence is needed to express the annotated content. Mark only the core statement required to convey the relevant factor.
- If two relevant spans belong to the same label and are separated only by a short, irrelevant passage, they may be annotated as a single span, including the intervening text.

5. Annotation Tool

We use INCEPTION (version 35.2) as the annotation tool because of our previous experience with the platform, its suitability for implementing our annotation requirements, and its intuitive interface for annotators.

6. Annotation Scheme

The risk and protective factors included in this scheme should not be interpreted as equally weighted. Some represent comparatively stable background characteristics, whereas others are more dynamic and potentially modifiable through treatment. Relapse risk may be shaped both by the number and severity of factors present. The tables below provide an overview of all risk and protective factors included in the scheme, along with supporting literature, a short description, and an example for each factor. All examples in this document are either AI-generated or prepared by the authors. The complete artificial sessions can be found [here](#).

6.1 Risk Factors

Factor and Literature	Description	Example
RF0: Not specified	Factors that do not belong to any of the other categories.	
RF1: Sexual preference for children (Schuler et al., 2021; Babchishin et al., 2015)	Expressions of persistent sexual arousal by (pre- and/or early pubescent) children in fantasies while masturbation and/or contact to real children. Prioritize a higher RF than RF1 if it applies to the section at hand. Only use RF1 if attraction to children is explicitly stated (a statement such as “ <i>I prefer CSAM over porn showing adults because I get turned on more</i> ” cannot be annotated with RF1).	<i>“I think it started in my late teens. I’ve had thoughts about younger kids, but I’ve never acted on them. I don’t want to. But I feel ashamed all the time, like I’m broken or something.”</i>
RF1.1: Sexual preference for male children (Seto and Eke, 2015)	Criteria as in RF1 , but specifically mentioning attraction to male children. This poses an additional risk. If this applies, it has priority over RF1 , as it is more specific.	<i>“For a long time, I hated myself for it. The fact that I’m only attracted to boys made me feel like I was broken. I kept hoping it would change, that maybe if I ignored it, it would go away. But it never did.”</i>

<p>RF2: Intimacy deficits, lack of trustful social relationships (Babchishin et al., 2023; Hart and Boer, 2020)</p>	<p>Lacking intimacy and trustful contacts with other persons. It comes along with loneliness and a lack of fulfillment of basic social needs and often leads to dysfunctional coping or regulation mechanisms. Indicators can be no intimate relationships, no or very few close (trustful) friends combined with feeling unhappy about it. Do not annotate “being a hermit” or alone and being happy about it as RF2.</p>	<p><i>“I’ve been struggling with urges that I know are wrong. It scares me. I feel like I can’t talk to anyone about this, but I don’t want to hurt anyone. I just don’t know what to do.”</i></p>
<p>RF 2.1: Being in a dysfunctional relationship (Babchishin et al., 2023; Hart and Boer, 2020)</p>	<p>Being in a relationship where intimacy needs are not fulfilled/ relationship conflicts. It can also contain a shame-based approach to sexuality within the relationship. If this applies, it has priority over RF2, as it is more specific.</p>	<p><i>“I just don’t feel very connected to my boyfriend. It is not like we have many deep conversations or intimate moments together these days... Whenever I wanna talk to him, he seems really absent-minded.”</i></p>
<p>RF3: Avoidance, suppression, missing acceptance of the sexual preference (Hart and Boer, 2020)</p>	<p>This usually leads to missing awareness and reflection of the inclination and enhances the risk to turn fantasies into behavior. Avoiding sexual fantasies with children can sometimes reflect on the behavioral level, as it might feel more comfortable to watch an image that is not your own instead of acknowledging your own sexual fantasies. RF3 also contains shame related to the preference. Do not annotate shame related to the consumption of CSAM or very high frequency of adult pornography as RF3. When poor mental health is the result of missing acceptance of the sexual preference, use RF3 instead of RF7.</p>	<p><i>“I think it started in my late teens. I’ve had thoughts about younger kids, but I’ve never acted on them. I don’t want to. But I feel ashamed all the time, like I’m broken or something.”</i></p> <p><i>“I have ruminated so much about why it has to be me who is attracted to children and how I can change that. My biggest wish is that this goes away one day. I just want to be normal.”</i></p>

<p>RF4: Dysfunctional coping (strategies) (Hart and Boer, 2020)</p>	<p>Coping with unpleasant feelings in a way that focuses on the maximum short-term gratification often leads to behavioral problems such as consumption of CSAM (sexualized coping), but also others like gambling, substance abuse etc. Individuals often do not recognize this as a problematic pattern and stumble into the vicious cycle repeatedly (downward spiral). It's a stress-driven behavior. To determine whether a certain behavior is a coping behavior, ask whether a feeling is regulated through the coping behavior. Typical phrases that indicate RF4 are "compulsive" or "addictive". RF4 includes specific recent situations (which happened after the last session or not earlier than 6 weeks before the first session) and not general reflections of typical behavior.</p>	<p><i>"I distract myself, mostly. I work long hours, drink sometimes to take the edge off, or just avoid people altogether. But none of it really works."</i></p> <p><i>"When I have stress at work or with my dad, who I am caring for, I also withdraw into my sexual fantasies a lot more. It is really annoying because it also makes me give in to watching videos with children more quickly."</i></p>
<p>RF4.1: Lack of impulse control</p>	<p>Not recognizing that certain stimuli trigger dysfunctional behaviors and that there is the possibility to control that behavior. If this applies, it has priority over RF4, as it is more specific.</p>	<p><i>"Luckily, last week, I did not specifically look for any videos with children in a sexual context. But when I went on TikTok, I saw a bunch of reels with teenage girls and I could not help it to use them for masturbation."</i></p>
<p>RF5: Reduction of cognitive dissonance, cognitive validation of problematic behavior (Hart and Boer, 2020; Bartels and Merdian, 2016; Mann et al., 2010; Marziano et al., 2006)</p>	<p>Offence-supportive attitudes and minimisations that reduce perceived wrongfulness or harm of CSAM consumption.</p>	<p><i>"I know I shouldn't watch these videos, but while I do watch them, I am just really happy and I really enjoy them. Then I also start to think "this is normal, everyone watches videos they like" or "there is no shame in desires". The videos are already existing, if I don't pay, I don't contribute to the production and distribution, so I do not harm anyone."</i></p>

<p>RF6: Past problematic behavior, criminal history (Helmus et al., 2025; Eke et al., 2019; Babchishin et al., 2015)</p>	<p>Repeated use of explicit sexual material depicting (pre- and/or early pubescent) children. The prior use of CSAM, and maybe even the severity, frequency and quantity of engagement in CSAM predict relapse. It does not matter how long ago the consumption occurred, however, annotate CSAM use since the last session as Relapse Behavior. It only refers to illegal content, do not annotate e.g. legal FKK magazines including children. Statements such as “<i>Erotic image of a teenage girl</i>” do not necessarily indicate problematic behavior. It could be a normal image that the person subjectively interprets as erotic. Only annotate RF6 if it is explicitly stated that CSAM was consumed, not if the patient stated that they wished to do so.</p>	<p><i>“The last time I consumed illegal videos was when I visited my brother and his family in their new house last year.”</i></p>
<p>RF7: Comorbidities, low well-being, other psychological problems or diseases (Babchishin et al., 2023; Hart and Boer, 2020)</p>	<p>Existence of other problems/diseases such as missing self-confidence, depression (mainly mood and drive problems), personality disorders, OCD, substance abuse disorders or problems, psychosis, etc. When poor mental health is the result of missing acceptance of the sexual preference, use RF3 instead of RF7.</p>	<p><i>“Stress is a big one. When I feel lonely or hopeless, the thoughts get worse. I’ve also had a hard time dealing with my own past. I was abused as a kid, and sometimes I wonder if that’s why I’m like this.”</i></p>
<p>RF8: Poor therapy and change commitment, missing confidence about reaching the goals and changing behavior (Hart and Boer, 2020)</p>	<p>Patient might be late for session, not engaging in the conversation, etc.</p>	<p><i>“I have tried to use the coping strategies, but they don’t really seem to work out, so I am getting less optimistic that this is gonna help at all.”</i></p>
<p>RF8.1: Directing responsibility to someone else (Hart and Boer, 2020)</p>	<p>Externalizing problems.</p>	<p><i>“I wanna tell my wife, but she is just really difficult to talk to. I think she needs therapy herself, so I guess I am helpless.”</i></p>

<p>RF9: Sociodemographic factors (Hart and Boer, 2020; Seto and Eke, 2015)</p>	<p>Young age and structural instability (e.g. financial issues, discontentness/ dissatisfaction with their professional or housing/living situation). Age criterion (the younger the individual, the higher the probability of a relapse) is based on clinical experience rather than empirical evidence. This relates to the current age, not the age at the first problematic behavior. RF9 should be prioritized over RF7 if poor mental health is the result of structural instability.</p>	<p><i>“I’m really not happy with where I am professionally right now. Work feels unfulfilling, and on top of that, I’m struggling to make ends meet financially.”</i></p>
<p>RF10: Hypersexuality, sexual preoccupation (Mann et al., 2010)</p>	<p>This includes anything that relates to an above average sex drive, general high engagement in sexual activities and fantasies.</p>	<p><i>“Almost everyday I spend hours reading erotic texts and subsequently watching porn. It takes up a lot of my time.”</i></p>
<p>RF10.1: Failure to satisfy sexual needs in a healthy way (Helmus et al., 2025; Baskurt et al., 2025)</p>	<p>E.g. handling of sexual urges /unhealthy sexual coping including misleading pre-assumptions about sex.</p>	<p><i>“I’m trying to do a challenge to stop all forms of sexual thoughts and masturbation.”</i></p>
<p>RF11: Hostility, preoccupation towards other groups (Malamuth et al., 1996)</p>	<p>E.g. misogyny/stereotyped thinking.</p>	<p><i>“I actually think that when women get upset when their partners tell them about sexual fantasies involving children, it is not really because they find it inappropriate... it rather stems from jealousy.”</i></p>
<p>RF12: Compulsive sexualization of non-sexual content (of children) and/or situations (with children)</p>	<p>Interpreting situations, pictures, videos preferably in a sexual way.</p>	<p><i>“Often I look at women on the bus and when they look back at me, I get really turned on and start imagining approaching them and what they would look like naked.”</i> <i>“My colleague brought her 12-year old son to work the other day. He just looked incredibly cute and attractive while he played on his phone. I really wanted to take a picture of him to use it for myself later.”</i></p>

6.2 Protective Factors

Factor/ Literature	Description	Example
<p>PF1: Non-exclusivity of the sexual preference for children (Ward et al., 2025; Willis and Ward, 2024; Thornton et al., 2024)</p>	<p>Additional sexual preference for adults. Only applicable in conjunction with RF1, a preference for adult persons can be protective as it allows easier healthy intimacy with adult persons.</p>	<p><i>“That part feels... different. Less shameful. I’ve dated women before, and it felt normal, like how it’s supposed to be. But the other part? I just want it gone.”</i></p>
<p>PF2: Healthy intimacy, trustful social relationships and acknowledgement of the importance of it (Ward et al., 2025)</p>	<p>Social support, fulfilled intimacy needs (in a romantic relationship or with close friends), or individually low and fulfilled needs for social interactions. Also annotate when visits to family or friends are mentioned in a neutral way, without any positive evaluation. Only annotate being in a romantic relationship as PF2 if it is mentioned in a positive way. Also annotate if the person expresses a desire for intimacy and considers it important.</p>	<p><i>“I’m pretty close with my sister, and I like painting. It helps me focus and quiet my mind sometimes.”</i></p> <p><i>“I know that pushing away people and not letting anyone get close to me leads me to fall back into old patterns.”</i></p>
<p>PF3: Acceptance of the sexual preference (Von Franqué et al., 2023; Beier et al., 2015)</p>	<p>Integration of the sexual preference into the self-image leads to better acknowledgement and reflection of the own individual risk, it enhances self-acceptance and well-being and reduces the need to cope with unpleasant feelings. Also annotate if the patient is aware of the importance of acceptance.</p>	<p><i>“Exactly. I know now that I can’t change what I’m attracted to. But I can change how I respond to it. I don’t have to let it control me.”</i></p>

<p>PF4: Functional coping (strategies) (Lätth et al., 2022; Marlatt and Donovan, 2005)</p>	<p>Active, reflective emotional self-care involves intentionally supporting one’s well-being and managing difficult emotions in ways that do not harm oneself or others, like e.g. self-help groups. It is often expressed through engaging in enjoyable or meaningful activities and recognizing their positive impact on coping with challenges. It also applies when the therapist restates or reflects a behavior described by the patient. However, it does not apply when the therapist is merely making a suggestion or recommendation for future actions. Also annotate the patient being aware of the importance of functional coping (without the presence of a concrete behavior) or hypothetical ideas for functional coping.</p>	<p><i>“I’m pretty close with my sister, and I like painting. It helps me focus and quiet my mind sometimes.”</i></p>
<p>PF4.1: Recognition and functional handling of impulses</p>	<p>Impulse control takes place in between the impulse to react to an arousing stimulus and the actual behavior. The urge to react is recognized and dealt with. If this applies, it has priority over PF4, as it is more specific. The recognition of an impulse should also be annotated, even if CSAM was consumed. PF4.1 often includes situation-analyses, in which past problematic behavior is reflected on.</p>	<p><i>“So I went on Instagram and I knew beforehand that I might see a few pictures that would trigger an urge in me to masturbate. So I thought to myself “when I see a young boy, instead of following that urge I will count until ten and then think what I will do”. And that is what I did.”</i></p> <p><i>“Workwise, if something isn’t going well and I have little control over it and that stresses me and I land on viewing CSAM as a way to control something.”</i></p>

<p>PF5: Recognition of the abuse of children in the material</p>	<p>Recognizing the harmful consequences of CSAM consumption for the children depicted in CSAM. If the person does not explicitly state that CSAM consumption is problematic because of the abuse, it should be assumed that they perceive the issue primarily as a problem for themselves (e.g. because of legal consequences).</p>	<p><i>“The thought of watching porn with children involved really excites me. But then I start thinking “this is real children, it’s nothing better than watching someone rape their child”.”</i></p>
<p>PF6: Healthy sexual behavior</p>	<p>E.g., masturbation with fantasies and no material, engaging in healthy and satisfying intimacy with adult partners, abstinence of problematic material for any reason. Any non-problematic behavior (which does not cause harm to yourself or others) counts as healthy behavior. Being aware of the importance of healthy sexual behavior (without concrete behavior) should also be annotated. Legal sexual content (e.g., adult pornography) could be an entry point for abuse imagery or healthy coping, thus the context must be considered.</p>	<p><i>“I really enjoy it when my partner gives me a massage. It also often ends in us having sex and I really like how connected we feel then.”</i></p>
<p>PF6.1: Abstinence of problematic behaviors due to a fear of legal consequences</p>	<p>Specifically stating that (illegal) problematic behaviors are avoided because of a fear of legal consequences. If this applies, it has priority over PF6, as it is more specific. Difference to PF10: PF6.1 is about abstinence, PF10 is about conscious healthy behavior.</p>	<p><i>“I know these videos are bad and will get me into trouble. I don’t use them anymore because I am too scared of the police getting involved.”</i></p>
<p>PF7: Well-being</p>	<p>E.g., positive responses to questions like “How are you feeling?”. Does not include empty phrases like “How are you? - I am fine, thanks”. Ensuring structural well-being and stability for the future should be annotated as PF7.</p>	<p><i>“Honestly... better than I expected. I’ve been sticking to my routines, exercising more, and trying to stay engaged with work. The thoughts are still there, but they don’t control me the way they used to.”</i></p>

<p>PF8: Cooperation with the therapist/ commitment to the treatment or study setting (Miller, 2023; Ewbank et al., 2021; Magill et al., 2018)</p>	<p>This includes being on time, answering questionnaires that are part of the intervention on time, actively participating in the treatment, fostering change of behavior between the sessions, doing homework, taking care of tasks, etc. Being aware of the importance of commitment and cooperation without the presence of a concrete behavior should also be annotated.</p>	<p><i>“I reminded myself why I stopped in the first place. I don’t want to go back to that. It makes me feel guilty, and I know it’s harmful. Instead, I forced myself to go outside for a walk, listen to music—just do something.”</i></p>
<p>PF8.1: Therapist’s affirmation of commitment</p>	<p>If this applies, it has priority over PF8, as it is more specific.</p>	<p><i>“It is really remarkable how you manage to stick to your coping strategies in difficult situations.”</i></p>
<p>PF10: Skills to satisfy sexual needs (urges) in a healthy way without harming themselves and/ or others (Lätth et al., 2022)</p>	<p>This includes being aware of the importance of skills to satisfy sexual needs in a healthy way, without the presence of a concrete behavior. Legal sexual content (e.g., adult pornography) could be an entry point for abuse imagery or healthy coping, thus the context must be considered.</p>	<p><i>“So I have learned to kind of put on these glasses while consuming porn... I watch porn that only contains adults but I try to turn them into children in my mind.”</i></p>

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